

COMPARISON OF THE MECHANICAL PROPERTY AND THE BALLISTIC BEHAVIOR IN HERACRON[®]/PHENOL COMPOSITE VIA PLASMA TREATMENT

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1 Introduction

Aramid, [PPTA; poly(p-phenylene terephthalamide)], fiber consists of relatively rigid polymer chain with benzene ring and amide bond. This unique structure gives the aramid fiber high tenacity, high modulus and toughness [1-3]. These features caused it to be used in the field of armory, aviation and automobile as one of the material for fiber-reinforced composite[4-7]. Among the various kinds of application, it is used mostly in the field of military materials, such as helmet, vest, plate, are major application fields of aramid fibers, until now.

In the fiber-reinforced composites, the interfacial adhesion between the matrix and fiber plays a very important role in determining their final mechanical properties. Generally, better fiber/matrix interfacial adhesion can induce to the improved tensile strength, interlaminar shear strength, and fatigue property [8, 9]. However, application with aramid fiber composites have been limited by poor fiber-matrix interfacial adhesion, since aramid fiber surface not only have no sufficient reactive functional groups for covalent bonding with matrix resin, but also possess the low surface energy [10-12].

In order to enhance the aramid/matrix adhesion, a various surface modifications have been applied, such as chemical treatment (including coupling agent and chemically grafting methods), enlargement of physical interface, such as mechanical interlocking and chemical activation of the fiber surface. The mechanism of these methods can be explained to increase the concentration of reactive functional groups or roughen the surface of the fiber [13, 14].

Among above methods, plasma, an ionized gas with essentially an equal density of negative and positive charge, is one of the most versatile techniques in polymer surface modification, because plasma

treatment may modify the uppermost atomic layers of the material surface without affecting its main characteristics. Most researchers employ the plasma treatment to improve the roughness of the fiber surface, resulting in the improved fiber/matrix adhesion [15, 16].

However, little has been reported in detail that the correlation of the mechanical property and interfacial adhesion on the aramid-reinforced composites via plasma treatment. Further, no one has examined a comparison study of their ballistic property with mechanical property along the strength of interfacial adhesion. In this study, aramid/phenol composites were prepared by the plasma treatment and influence of plasma treatment on their mechanical property and ballistic behavior were ascertained. It is anticipated that this study provides fundamental information on how interfacial adhesion regulate the mechanical property and ballistic behavior on the aramid-reinforced composites.

2 Experimental

2.1 Material

Aramid fabric(weaves : plain, areal density : 155 g/m²) used in this study was woven from Heracron[®] fiber(fiber's linear density : 600 denier), which is product of KOLON Industries, INC. The phenol resin was provided by KOLON Industries, INC. PVB(Poly vinyl butyral) was supplied by Kuraray Specialist Europe, which is used as toughening agent. The aramid fabric was washed via the scouring process to eliminate finishing oil and surface contamination.

2.2 Plasma treatment

A bell-shaped plasma treatment system was constructed using a direct current power source

MDX-1K from Advanced Energy Industry, INC. 100 % oxygen plasma was generated at 2000 W under 65 mTorr. The oxygen gas flow rate was set at 1000 sccm. The Heracron[®] fabric samples were then treated by the oxygen plasma for 10 and 20 min. without any extra heating. After the treatment, the samples were conserved in a dry box until any analysis.

2.3 Heracron[®]/phenol composite preparation

The Heracron[®]/phenol composites were fabricated with O₂ plasma treated/non-treated Heracron[®] fabrics, which were resin-dipped. Mixture of phenol and PVB(75:25, weight ratio) was used as dipping resin. The dipped fabrics were cured at 150 °C for 5 min. under certain pressure. The relative mass fraction of the fabrics in the composites was about 77 %.

2.4 Ballistic helmet preparation

The ballistic helmets for the test were fabricated by Daesung Tech., Inc, Korea.

2.5 Analysis

To determine the change of surface energy of Heracron[®] fabric before and after plasma treatment, the water contact angle was measured by Contact Angle System OCA40 from Data Physics Instrument. X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy(XPS) was performed with ESCALAB 250 photoelectron spectrometer equipped with an MgK α (1253.6 eV) X-ray source. The surface morphology of plasma treated Heracron[®] fabric and composite was observed by scanning electron microscopy (SEM, JSM-6700F, JEOL, Tokyo, Japan). For mechanical properties, ASTM D 3039, Test Method for Tensile Properties of Polymer Matrix Composite Materials, was provided as guidance. Helmets' ballistic test (V₅₀) was conducted in accordance with the provision of MIL-STD-662F, using caliber .22 (dia. 5.5 mm), 17 grain (1 grain = 0.0648 g) fragment simulating projectiles (FSP).

2.6 Sample code

In this article, sample codes are used to avoid unnecessary repetition of sample name. Sample codes are in Table 1.

3 Result and discussion

3.1 Plasma treatment of Heracron[®] fabrics

The water contact angle of plasma-untreated Heracron[®] fabric(Sample 1) was 79.4°. As Heracron[®] fabric was treated by plasma for longer time, the contact angle was reduced as in Figure 1. This indicates that the O₂ plasma treatment might lead to introduction of certain polar groups such as -COO- or -OH onto Heracron[®] fiber surface. This trend was also observed by XPS as shown in Figure 2.. It shows the increment of O1s peaks around the bonding energy of 533 eV. The bonding energy of functional groups such as -OH and -COO- is 533.7 eV and 534.3 eV. Furthermore, these two functional groups exist in the molecular structure of aramid. As the time of treatment was increased, the composition of carbon was gradually reduced, at the same time, that of oxygen was increased(Table 2.). It goes well with the result of the contact angle analysis that was already shown in Figure 1.. In Figure 3., the surface images of plasma treated and non-treated fabric are provided. As the fabric was treated by plasma for longer time(from 0 min.(a) to 20 min. (c)), the surface of the fiber got roughened. It'd be possible that the period of treatment by plasma has some relationship with the extent of the amount of fiber's surface oxidation. Wu et al studied that the roughness of the fiber surface might cause stronger mechanical interlock between fiber and matrix[17]. However, it should be considered that too much treatment would provoke ablation or the etching effect to the fabric to cause the reduction of the fabric strength. So, the mechanical properties of the fabric were measured with a provision of ISO 13934-1. As in Table 3, little damage from plasma treatment was observed. Despite occurrence of little damage on fabric's mechanical properties, it's clear that the treatment of plasma caused somewhat reduction in its strength due to the structural deformation of plasma exposed fiber

3.2 Heracron[®]/Phenol composites

In general, the mechanical properties of fiber-reinforced composites are strongly dependent to the degree of interfacial adhesion between fiber and matrix. Analysis by SEM was carried out to easily measure the degree of interfacial adhesion between Heracron[®] and phenol. As shown in Figure 4, plasma treatment is considered to be capable of improving the interfacial adhesion between Heracron[®] fiber and phenol. Moreover, the data in Table 4. indicate that sample 3FPC exhibited better mechanical properties. It might be explained by the degree of interfacial adhesion between 2 different material and as shown in Figure 4., 3FPC's adhesion force was strong enough to compensate for the weakness caused by defects on fabric's surface.

3.3 Ballistic properties of Heracron[®]/Phenol composite based helmets

The ballistic test of Heracron[®]/phenol composites based helmets was carried out. 2 set of samples were prepared. 1st set was composed with 2 kinds of helmets that have different number of layers and those helmets were fabricated with 1FPC. 2nd set had same composition as 1st set, but the material used for fabrication was 3FPC. Analyzing the result of ballistic test, something unexpected was discovered. That is, despite the increment of mechanical properties of plasma treated fabric resulted from interfacial adhesion between fabric and phenol, the test results in Table 5. seem to exhibit decrement of ballistic ability when the sample was prepared with plasma treated fabric. It could be explained as follow; In general, when a layer of neat fabric is shot by a bullet, the fabric deforms transversely and expansion of space between warps and wefts is occurred. This phenomenon is called 'wedge through'[18]. Assuming the fabric structure is the same, the ballistic ability depends on the yarn's mobility. In other words, yarns that have enough space to move are capable of absorbing the impact caused from the bullet by dispersing it to the yarn beside. The plasma treated fabric, however, isn't able to absorb the impact due to the low mobility

resulted from strong adhesion between the fiber and the resin. In other words, the whole energy from the bullet might be delivered to tiny area when compared with non-treated fabric. The schematic diagram of impact energy dispersion of Heracron[®]/phenol composites is shown in Figure 5.

4 Conclusion

In this investigation, we could notify that the treatment of O₂ plasma to the Heracron[®] fabric increased its affinity to phenol resin by introducing several functional groups to its surface. As expected, the plasma treated fabric demonstrated higher physical properties than non-treated one. The ballistic ability, however, was reduced due to the restriction of mobility caused from excess interfacial adhesion. It's obvious that the optimal treatment condition should be investigated in further research.

5 References

- [1] Yang H., "Kevlar aramid fiber", John Wiley & Sons Ltd, Baffins Lane, Chichester West Sussex PO191UD, England, 1993
- [2] Pieter J., Peter G., Edith M., Warawan P., Robert J., "Controlled interfacial adhesion of twaron aramid fibers in composites by the finish formulation", *Compos.Sci. Technol.*, 67, pp 2027-2035, 2007
- [3] Rao Y., Waddon A., Farris R., "The evaluation of structure and properties in poly(p-phenylene terephthalamide) fibers", *Polymer*, 42, pp 5925-5935, 2001
- [4] Yue C., Padmanabhan K., "Interfacial studies on surface modified kevlar fibre/epoxy matrix composites", *Composite Part B*, 30, pp 205-217, 1999
- [5] Lin T., Wu S., Lai J., Shyu S., "The effect of chemical treatment on reinforcement/matrix interaction in kevlar-fiber/bismaleide composites", *Compos.Sci. Technol.*, 60, pp 1873-1878, 2000
- [6] Kawagoe M., Takeshima M., Nomiya M., Qiu J., Morita M., Mizuno W., Kitano H., "Microspectroscopic evaluations of the interfacial degradation by absorbed water in a model composites of an aramid and unsaturated polyester", *Polymer*, 40, pp 373-1380, 1999
- [7] Park R., Jang J., "Impact behavior of aramid fiber/glass fiber hybrid composites; the effect of staking sequence", *Polymer composite*, 22, pp 80-89, 2001

[8] Kalantar J., Drzal L., “The bonding mechanism of aramid fibers to epoxy matrix”, *Journal of materials science*, pp 25-4186, 1990

[9] Wu J., Cheng X., “Interfacial studies on the surface modified aramid fiber reinforced epoxy composites”, *Journal of applied polymer science*, 102, pp 4165-4170, 2006

[10] Lin J., “Effect of surface modification by bromination and metalation on kevlar fibre-epoxy adhesion”, *European polymer journal*, 38, pp 79-86, 2002

[11] Lee, S., Chian K., Yue C., Looi H., “Effects of bromination and hydrolysis treatment on the morphology and tensile properties of kevlar-29 fibers”, *J.Mater. Sci. Lett.*, 13, pp 305-309, 1994

[12] Rebouillat S., Peng J., Dommet J., “Surface structure of kevlar fiber studied by atomic force microscopy and inverse gas chromatography”, *Polymer*, 40, pp 7341-7350, 1999

[13] Inagaki N., Tasaka S., Kawai H., Yamada Y., “Surface modification of aromatic polyamide film by remote oxygen plasma”, *J. Appl. Polym. Sci.*, 64, pp 831-840, 1997

[14] Breznick M., Banbaji J., Baklagina Y., “Surface treatment technique for aramid fibers”, *Polym. Commun.*, 28, pp 55-60, 1987

[15] Wu. G., “Oxygen plasma treatment of high performance fiber for composites”, *Materials Chemistry and Physics*, 85, pp 81-87, 2004

[16] Li R., Ye L., Mai Y., “Application of plasma technologies in reinforced polymer composites; a review of recent development”, *Compos. Part A- Appl. S.*, 28, pp 73-86, 1997

[17] Wu G., Hung C., Lu J., “Effects of plasma treatment on high performance fibers for composites”, *SAMPE*, 44, pp 1090-1097, 1999

[18] Montgomery T., Grady P., Tomasino C., “The effects of projectile geometry on the performance of ballistics fabrics”, *Text. Res. J.*, 52, pp 442-500, 1982

	Plasma-untreated	Plasma treated (10 min.)	Plasma treated (20 min.)
Fabric	1	2	3
Fabric/Phenol Composite	1FPC	2FPC	3FPC
Helmet	1HM	2HM	3HM

Table 1. Sample code table

Sample	Contact Angle (°)	Figure
Plasma-untreated Heracron®	79.4	
Plasma-treated Heracron® (10min)	52.5	
Plasma-treated Heracron® (20min)	40.7	

Fig. 1. The analysis of water contact angle of O₂ plasma treated fabric and untreated fabric

Fig. 2. XPS analysis of O₂ plasma treated fabric

Condition	Chemical composition (%)			Atomic ratio
	C1s	O1s	The rest component	O/C
1	82.4	12.6	5.0	0.153
2	78.5	15.4	6.1	0.196
3	73.5	19.2	7.3	0.261

Table 2. Chemical composition and atomic ratio of O₂ plasma treated fabric

Fig. 3. SEM images of O₂ plasma treated and untreated fabric(fiber)

Fig. 5. The schematic diagram of impact energy dispersion

Sample	Property	Max. Force (N)	Tensile Strength (MPa)	Elongation at break (%)
1		2660± 20	450±5	4.6 ±2
2		2650± 20	445±5	4.6±2
3		2650± 20	445±5	4.5±2

Table 3. Mechanical properties of O₂ plasma treated and untreated fabric

Fig. 4. SEM images of composites produced with O₂ plasma treated and untreated Heracron[®] fabric

Sample	Tensile strength (N/mm ²)	Max. load (N)	Yield Strength (N/mm ²)	Yield. load (N)	Modulus (N/mm ²)
1FPC	438	2411	400	2203	15700
3FPC	470	2683	440	2306	16600

Table 4. Mechanical properties of Heracron[®]/phenol composites

Property	Sample		Sample	
	1HM		3HM	
	A	B	C	D
Weight (g)	1183	1274	1180	1279
Ply	49	54	49	54
Resin content (%)	23		23	
V ₅₀ (m/s)	609.3	693.2	579.3	647.7

Table 5. Ballistic behavior of Heracron[®]/phenol composites based helmets